

ETHYLENE OXYACETYLATION REACTION KINETICS LEARN.

Toshboyev Feruz Nizomiddinovich¹.,
Akhmadov Javokhir Zoirovich²
Eshonqulov Zoyirjon Axmadovich³

¹Samarkand State Medical University, ²Samarkand State Medical University resident of magistracy Department of Pharmaceutical and Toxicological Chemistry, SamDVMCHBU akademik litseyi³
Samarkand, Uzbekistan

*e-mail: toshboyev122@gmail.com

Annotation . The main direction of the republic's economic development is the development of natural resources, their rational use, and complete modernization. It consists of technical and technological upgrading of industrial enterprises, introduction of modern scientific achievements and innovative technologies, production of products with high added value that can replace competitive imports and are constantly appreciated in the international market. Creation of waste-free and environmentally friendly technology in chemical enterprises, introduction of new methods of processing industrial waste to enterprises is an urgent problem for scientists and engineers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Key words: Vinylacetate, catalyst, 95-92 % , selectivity , 750-670g , CH₃COOH , CO₂ , Pd, CH₃COOK and Cu .

The purpose of our research is to study the kinetics of processes for the oxyacetylation reaction of higher ethylene .

Research object : acetylene , vinegar acid , zinc acetate , cadmium acetate , zirconium oxide , ceramsite is considered

Intensification of production of existing vinyl acetate from acetylene and improvement of its technical and economic indicators is of great practical importance. In industry, the traditional impregnation method of catalyst preparation is used, based on impregnation of coal with an aqueous solution of spirit acetate, followed by drying. As a result, sufficiently active and stable catalysts of vinyl acetate synthesis were obtained . [2,4]

Research method: Generalized mathematical relationships, defined as the rates of formation of vinyl acetate and CO₂, allowing to calculate the optimal composition of the catalyst with let's meet :

$$W_{VA} = [Pd] (35 + 38 [CH_3COOK] + 4.2 [Cu]) : (1 + 0.05(1 + 80 [Pd])^4 + 0.01 [CH_3COOK]^2 + 1.1 [Cu]),$$

$$W_{CO_2} = [Pd] (0.09 + 0.024 [CH_3COOK] + 0.1 [Cu]) / (1 + 0.07(1 + 20 [CH_3COOK]) [Pd]^3). [2,3]$$

show the stability of their activity and selectivity over time. The activities of the catalysts are 340-290, 550-480, 550-480, 95-92% selectivity of vinylacetate formation on ethylene, respectively.

750-670g Vinyl acetate formed / (l·cat·hour).

$$W_{VA} = \frac{P(O_2) \times P(\text{эТ})}{C_1 + C_2 \cdot P + C_3 \cdot P \cdot P} \text{mol/h [2,3]}$$

$$W_{CO_2} = \frac{P(\text{эТ})}{C_4 + C_5 \cdot P \cdot P} \text{mol/h [1.3]}$$

Here, C₁-C₅: ethylene and CH₃COOH are functions of sorption coefficients on the catalyst, which may depend on the ratio of reagents. The appearance of C₂ indicates the monosorption of ethylene or acetic acid, and the appearance of C₃ and C₅ carbohydrates indicates the quadratic sorption of these reagents in the active centers of the catalyst.[4]

Conclusion: In the experimental series, the obtained rates and calculated values of the formation reaction are correlated according to these relationships. Formation reaction rates Vinylacetate – 0.98, CO₂ - 0.92. Using the dependences of the activity of the catalyst on the components stored in it (Pd, CH₃COOK and Cu), their optimal amount was determined to achieve high activity and selectivity of vinylacetate formation. Analysis of kinetic data can provide valuable information about the reaction mechanism. Unfortunately, the kinetic equations (given by us above) were obtained at atmospheric pressure, and therefore they cannot serve as a reliable basis for understanding the mechanism.

In general, in the literature there are few works devoted to the development of a mathematical model of the ethylene - based process . It is possible to obtain quantitative information about how the productivity and selectivity of the catalyst change when the composition of the initial mixture and the process parameters change .

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